

Cardio-Protection Potentials of N-Hexane Extract of *Annona Muricata* Leaves on Isoniazid Induced Heart Damage in Wistar Rats

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doi:10.5281/zenodo.16050245

Abstract: This study investigated the potential protective effects of the n-hexane extract of *Annona muricata* leaves on isoniazid induced cardiac damage in wistar rats using selected cardiac biomarkers and tissue antioxidants. Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), creatine kinase (CK), total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), high density lipoprotein (HDL) and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) alongside superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione (GSH), and malondialdehyde (MDA) were assayed for using standard methods. Completely randomized block design (CRBD) was used for this study. A total of 25 wistar rats with weights ranging from 200g to 300g were divided into five groups, each comprising of 5 rats. The rats were acclimatized for 14 days before treatment as follows: Group 1 (normal control) and group 2 (positive control) were administered distilled water throughout the experiment while groups 3, 4 and 5 were pretreated with 200 mg/kg extract, 400 mg/kg extract and 200 mg/kg vitamin E respectively. Groups 2,3,4 and 5 were administered 50mg/kg of isoniazid after daily pretreatment for 21 days to induce heart damage. All treatments were administered via oral administration. At the 22nd day, the experimental animals were euthanised under chloroform anaesthesia and blood samples were collected through cardiac puncture for assessment of heart function. Some parts of the heart tissues were homogenized for antioxidant analysis. The results indicated that pretreatment with *Annona muricata* n-hexane leaf extract (at doses of 200 mg/kg body weight and 400 mg/kg body weight) did not significantly cause a change in the mean weight of the experimental subjects when compared to the normal group. Isoniazid-intoxication resulted in a significant increase in LDH, CK, TC, TG, LDL, and MDA levels, while HDL, SOD, CAT, and GSH showed a significant decrease when compared to the normal control group. However, pretreatment with *Annona muricata* extract led to significant elevations in SOD, CAT, GSH, and HDL levels, alongside a significant decrease in LDH, CK, TC, TG, LDL and MDA levels when compared to the positive control group. Similarly, administering Vitamin E at a dose of 200mg/kg also resulted in significant increase in SOD, CAT, GSH, and HDL levels, coupled with a decrease in LDH, CK, TC, TG, MDA, and LDL levels when compared to the positive control group. In conclusion, the findings of this study strongly suggest that the n-hexane leaf extract of *Annona muricata* may contain antioxidant compounds that could offer cardioprotective effects on wistar rats subjected to cardiac damage induced by isoniazid.

Keywords: Cardiac, Antioxidant, *Annona muricata*, Isoniazid and Biomarker.

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Received: June 6, 2024

Revised: August 27, 2024

Accepted: September 27, 2024

Cite this Paper as:

About the Journal: SJANS is a multidisciplinary science journal and the official journal of the Faculty of Science, Nigeria Police Academy, Kano, Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

Plants have been valued since ancient times for their therapeutic properties, forming the basis of global herbal medicine systems. Herbal medicine utilizes various plant parts such as leaves, roots, and seeds to prevent and treat diseases (Ozioma and Okaka, 2019). Cultures worldwide, including Mesopotamia, Egypt, China, India, Greece and the Americas developed sophisticated herbal healing systems that are being passed down through generations (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2019). Each region has its unique repertoire of medicinal plants and healing traditions such as Ayurveda in India, Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), Native American herbalism and African

traditional medicine (Baskar *et al.*, 2007). Plants produce a wide range of bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and phenolics which have pharmacological properties beneficial to human health (Asare *et al.*, 2018). These phytochemicals serve functions within plants like defence against pests and pathogens and exhibit diverse biological activities when consumed by humans. Scientific interest in medicinal plants has grown with research focusing on understanding their mechanisms of action and conducting clinical trials to evaluate safety and efficacy (Elmas *et al.*, 2022).

However, challenges such as habitat destruction, overharvesting and regulatory complexities pose significant obstacles to their sustainable use

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

(Chang *et al.*, 2013). Despite challenges, medicinal plants represent a blend of traditional knowledge and modern scientific inquiry, offering potential for new healthcare innovations (Moghadamtousi *et al.*, 2015). *Annona muricata*, commonly known as soursop is one such plant revered for its medicinal uses and it is extensively studied for its pharmacological potentials (Parham *et al.*, 2020; Prasad *et al.*, 2019). Native to tropical regions, *Annona muricata* is characterized by its distinctive fruit and diverse therapeutic properties (Sofowora *et al.*, 2013).

2.0 Material and Method

2.1 Study area

The administration of treatment to the animal subjects was carried out in the animal the Department of Biochemistry, Niger Delta University. Similarly, the biochemical analysis took place at the Chemical Pathology Laboratory of the Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, Bayelsa State. Okolobiri is a rural village situated in the Yenagoa Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. With a population of over 20,000, it is essentially a riverine town located at 4.88540N and 6.07840E geographical coordinates. Okolobiri is a fast-developing suburb and is host several multinational oil companies and has been plagued by oil pollution for decades. The common vocation of natives and residents of Okolobiri are mainly farming, fishing, petty traders, company workers and civil servants (Ikimi and Addy, 2024).

2.2 Collection and identification of plant sample

Fresh leaves *Annona muricata* were collected from the premises of College of Health Sciences, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State. The plant was identified by Professor Kola Ajibesin of the Department of Pharmacognosy, Faculty of Pharmacy, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State.

2.3 Preparation of plant extract

The plant leaves were collected in large quantity and left under shade at room temperature for 2 weeks to dry. Afterwards, they were ground into powder. Thereafter, 247g of the powder was soaked in 1.5litres of n-hexane and allowed to stand for 48hours. The extract was collected, filtered and concentrated under increased pressure using a rotary evaporator at 60°C and 40 rpm.

2.4 Animal specimen and study population

Twenty-five healthy male wistar rats weighing between 200g and 300g were used for this study. The animals were procured from the animal house of the University of Port Harcourt. The rats were kept in standard animal cages and acclimatized in the animal house, in the Department of Pharmacology, Niger Delta University, for 14 days and allowed free access to pelleted chicken feed and water. Mead's resource equation was utilized for the calculation of the sample size (Kirkwood and Robert, 2010). The equation is stated and the components defined. $E = N - B - T$, where: N is the total number of individuals or units in the study (minus 1). B is the blocking component, representing environmental effects allowed for in the design (minus 1). T is the treatment component, corresponding to the number of treatment groups (including control group) being used, or the number of questions being asked (minus 1). E is the degrees of freedom of the error component, and should be somewhere between 10 and 20. The study constituted of five groups (T = 4), with 5 animals per group, making 25 animals in total (N = 24), without any further stratification (B = 0), then E would equal 20, indicating that the sample size is very suitable for the research.

2.5 Ethical clearance

Ethical clearance was obtained from the animal research ethics committee of the Department of Biochemistry, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State. The Animal Welfare Act of 1985 of the United States of America for research and Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) protocols were stringently adhered to (Benjamin and Jean, 2016).

2.6 Experimental design

Completely randomized block design (CRBD) was used for this study. The animals were randomly grouped into 5 groups of 5 rats each in a standard rat cage and were treated as follows:

Group 1 (Normal control): were fed with only pelleted chicken feed and distilled water.

Group 2 (Positive control): were administered isoniazid (50 mg/kg) daily for 21 days.

Group 3 (Test group 1): were administered 200 mg/kg of plant extract + 50 mg/kg isoniazid for 21 days.

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

Group 4 (Test group 2): were administered 400mg/kg of plant extract + 50 mg/kg isoniazid for 21 days.

Group 5 (Standard control): were administered Vitamin E (200 mg/kg) + 50 mg/kg isoniazid for 21 days.

All groups were fed with pelleted chicken feed and distilled water *ad libitum*.

2.7 Selection criteria

Rats used were apparently healthy and active as confirmed and approved by a veterinary doctor. Rats showing signs and symptoms of illness were excluded from the research. Also excluded were rats with any form of derangements. Contaminated blood samples were rejected.

2.8 Collection and preparation of blood and tissue samples

Blood was collected via cardiac puncture into plain bottles and allowed to stand for 30mins for coagulation to take place so as to obtain only the serum. Afterwards, the blood samples were centrifuged for 10mins at 2000 rpm and the supernatant was collected for the analysis. A portion of the heart tissues was also collected to prepare the homogenate for the antioxidant assays (Sule *et al.*, 2017; Ness, 1999).

2.9 Analysis of samples

Serum lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity was estimated spectrophotometrically and quantified using Agappe method as modified by Agappe diagnostics (Switzerland) (Agappe kit leaflet); serum creatine kinase (CK) activity was estimated spectrophotometrically and quantified using Agappe method as modified by Agappe Diagnostics (Switzerland) (Agappe Kit Leaflet); serum total cholesterol (TC) concentration was estimated spectrophotometrically and quantified using Agappe kit as specified by Agappe Diagnostics (Switzerland) (Agappe Kit Leaflet); serum triacylglycerol (TG) concentration was estimated spectrophotometrically and quantified using Agappe kit as specified by Agappe Diagnostics (Switzerland) (Agappe Kit Leaflet) (Ikimi *et al.*, 2023; Ikimi *et al.*, 2024). Serum high density lipoprotein (HDL) concentration was measured spectrophotometrically and quantified using CHQD PAP assay method; serum low density lipoprotein (LDL) concentration was measured spectrophotometrically and quantified using CHQD PAP assay method (Miller *et al.*, 2010).

SOD activity was determined by the method of Xin *et al.*, (1991) as contained in Randox commercial kit leaflet; the method of Habig *et al.*, (1974) was followed in estimating the level of reduced glutathione (GSH); catalase (CAT) activity was determined according to the method of Aebi, (1983); lipid peroxidation analyses was carried out by determining the concentration of malondialdehyde (MDA) formed using the method of Varshney and Kale (1990), as modified and reported in Agoro *et al.*, 2017 and Agoro *et al.*, 2019.

2.10 Statistical analysis

Results were analysed statistically using One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) under Turkey Kramer Multiple Comparison Test and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Values are expressed as mean±standard deviation (SD) and were considered statistically significant at p< 0.05.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Result

Table 1: Effect of isoniazid and *Annona muricata* on the mean body weight (g) of wistar rats

Experimental group	Mean weight before treatment	Mean weight after treatment	% Mean weight change
Group 1 (Normal control)	158.6 ± 2.70	198.0 ± 11.02	24.84 ^a
Group 2 (Positive control)	159.8 ± 3.11	198.6 ± 8.70	24.28 ^a
Group 3 (Test group 1)	160.4 ± 3.04	201.8 ± 8.25	25.49 ^a
Group 4 (Test group 2)	159.8 ± 5.06	181.8 ± 36.05	13.64 ^b
Group 5 (Standard control)	162.4 ± 4.03	203.8 ± 3.76	25.49 ^a

Data are expressed as the mean ± SD (n = 5). Means within the same column carrying same superscripts are not significantly (p < 0.05) different.

Results (table 1) shows that pretreatment with *Annona muricata* 400 mg/kg body weight (test group 2) caused a significant (p<0.05) decrease in the rate of weight gain (13.64%) when compared with the normal (24.84%) and positive (24.28%) controls.

Table 2 shows that isoniazid administration caused a significant increase (p<0.05) in serum concentrations of LDH (43.25 ± 2.54^bU/L), CK (34.44 ± 0.8^bU/L), TC (126.14 ± 2.63^bmg/dl), TG (13.91 ± 1.37^b mg/dl) and LDL (95.23 ± 3.15^b

mg/dl) but a decrease in HDL (3.34±1.27^bmg/dl) (positive control) when compared to the normal control. However, pretreatment with *Annona muricata* at doses of 200 mg/kg body weight and 400 mg/kg body weight showed a significant (p<0.05) dose dependent decrease in serum concentrations of LDH (30.51± 3.05^{U/L} and 19.33± 0.64^{dU/L}), CK (20.25±1.49^{U/L} and 11.91±0.69^{U/L}), TC (107.49±8.76^cmg/dl and 90.90±1.99^d mg/dl), TG (7.01±0.11^c mg/dl and 5.63±0.29^a mg/dl) and LDL (73.31±3.15^cmg/dl and 56.95±2.64^dmg/dl) and a dose dependent increase in HDL (39.60±2.58^cmg/dl and 45.81±2.01^dmg/dl) respectively, relative to other isoniazid treated groups.

Table 2: Effects of *Annona muricata* on the levels of cardiac parameters in isoniazid induced heart damage in wistar rats

Experimental group	LDH (U/L)	CK (U/L)	TC (mg/dl)	TG (mg/dl)	HDL (mg/dl)	LDL (mg/dl)
Group 1 (Normal control)	11.95 ± 0.33 ^a	9.08 ± 0.3 ^a	75.07 ± 3.87 ^a	5.42 ± 0.2 ^a	58.4 ± 9.2 ^a	45.30 ± 3.46 ^a
Group 2 (Positive control)	43.25 ± 2.54 ^b	34.4 ± 4.0 ^b	126.1 ± 4.2 ^b	13.9 ± 1.1 ^b	3.34 ± 1.27 ^b	95.23 ± 3.15 ^b
Group 3 (Test group 1)	30.51 ± 3.05 ^c	20.2 ± 5.1 ^c	107.4 ± 9.8 ^c	7.01 ± 0.1 ^c	39.6 ± 0.2 ^c	73.31 ± 3.15 ^c
Group 4 (Test group 2)	19.33 ± 0.64 ^d	11.9 ± 1.0 ^d	90.90 ± 1.9 ^d	5.63 ± 0.2 ^d	45.8 ± 1.2 ^d	56.95 ± 2.64 ^d
Group 5 (Stand. control)	11.7 ± 0.23 ^a	10.0 ± 1.0 ^a	79.11 ± 3.8 ^a	5.58 ± 0.2 ^a	52.1 ± 7.1 ^a	54.02 ± 4.27 ^a

Data are expressed as the mean ± SD (n = 5). Means within the same column carrying same superscripts are not significantly (p < 0.05) different

Table 3: Antioxidant effects of *Annona muricata* on isoniazid induced heart damage in wistar rats

Exp. group	SOD U/mg	CAT U/mg	MDA U/mg	GSH U/mg
Group 1 (Normal control)	9.22± 0.46 ^a	7.27±0.29 ^a	2.01±0.10 ^a	7.11±0.54 ^a
Group 2 (Positive control)	2.44± 0.25 ^b	2.13±0.13 ^b	5.99±0.05 ^b	2.01±0.06 ^b
Group 3 (Test group 1)	4.08± 0.56 ^c	3.106±0.13 ^c	3.67±0.37 ^c	3.98±0.09 ^c
Group 4 (Test group 2)	5.53± 0.49 ^c	4.48±0.33 ^d	2.13±0.03 ^a	4.35±0.28 ^d
Group 5 (S/Control)	125.34± 266.46 ^d	4.75±0.21 ^d	2.09±0.07 ^a	4.72±0.25 ^d

Data are expressed as the mean ± SD (n = 5). Means within the same column carrying same superscripts are not significantly (p<0.05) different.

Table 3 shows that isoniazid administration caused a significant decrease (p<0.05) in heart SOD (2.44± 0.25^bU/mg), CAT (2.13±0.13^bU/mg) and GSH (2.01±0.06^bU/mg) activities and a significant increase (p<0.05) in heart MDA concentration (5.99±0.05^bU/mg) (positive control) relative to the normal control. However, pretreatment with *Annona muricata* at doses of 200 mg/kg body weight and 400 mg/kg body weight caused a significant (p<0.05) dose dependent elevation of heart activities of SOD (4.08± 0.56^cU/mg and 5.53± 0.49^cU/mg), CAT (3.106±0.13^cU/mg and 4.48±0.33^dU/mg) and GSH (3.98±0.09^cU/mg and 4.35±0.28^dU/mg) and a significant decrease in heart MDA (3.67±0.37^cU/mg and 2.13±0.03^aU/mg) concentrations respectively, relative to other isoniazid treated groups.

3.2 Discussion

Isoniazid is a cornerstone medication used in the treatment of tuberculosis. However, its use has been associated with several side effects, including hepatotoxicity and cardiotoxicity (Zango *et al.*, 2019). *Annona muricata*, commonly known as soursop, is a plant native to tropical regions with potential antioxidant and organo-protective properties (Chan *et al.*, 20200). This study aimed at investigating the protective effects of n-hexane extract of *Annona muricata* leaves on heart health in wistar rats treated with isoniazid, a medication used to treat tuberculosis. The findings indicated that pretreatment with *Annona muricata* 400 mg/kg body weight (test group 2) caused a significant (p<0.05) decrease in the rate of weight gain (13.64%) when compared with the normal (24.84%) and positive (24.28%) controls, suggesting potential weight management properties of the extract.

Isoniazid has been associated with appetite loss and weight reduction in humans (Omeje and Chime, 2019). Studies on the weight-related effects of *Annona muricata* are inconclusive. Some report anti-obesity properties, while others show no significant impact. The current data hints at potential weight reduction influence with high-dose *Annona muricata* (test group 2), yet further research is required for validation (Nwankpa *et al.*, 2017). Isoniazid increased LDH and CK activities alongside an increase in TC, TG and HDL levels when compared to the normal control, while *Annona muricata* (test groups 1 and 2) and vitamin E (standard control) reduced these levels, suggesting cardio-protective effects. The report of Aliyu and Adelaiye (2018) reiterated the cardiotoxic characteristic of isoniazid as one of its principal findings. While traditionally used for various health conditions, the scientific evidence for the heart-protective benefits of *Annona muricata* is limited (Afolabi and Ogunsanwo, 2018). The findings of this study provide empirical signals on the potential protective effects of *Annona muricata* leaves on heart health.

The observed cardio-protective effects were found to be dose-dependent, emphasizing the need for further studies to elucidate the precise mechanisms involved. The findings of this study may contribute towards resolving the uncertainty associated with the impact of *Annona muricata* on heart health (Zubaidi *et al.*, 2023). The observed biochemical effects of *Annona muricata*

(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

extract may be attributed to its phytochemical composition, which includes antioxidant compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins and cardiac glycosides, potentially providing cardio-protective effects against isoniazid-induced kidney injury in rats (Abdul-Wahab *et al.*, 2018). Antioxidants play a crucial role in preventing cellular damage caused by free radicals generated during various metabolic processes (Sharifi-Rad *et al.*, 2020). The study also assessed antioxidant parameters, revealing that isoniazid intoxication significantly increased kidney MDA concentration while reducing the activities of SOD, CAT and GSH enzymes, indicating heightened lipid peroxidation and compromised antioxidant defence mechanisms. Treatment with *Annona muricata* extract and vitamin E reversed these effects, suggesting antioxidant properties of the extract. These findings align with that of Umoren *et al.*, (2023), who demonstrated that *Annona muricata* leaf extract prevented hepato-renal toxicity in male wistar rats by enhancing in vivo antioxidant defences.

Conclusion

This study suggests that *Annona muricata* may offer a promising approach to mitigating the cardio-toxicity caused by isoniazid treatment. The partial restoration of antioxidant enzyme activity and the prevention of lipid peroxidation indicate a potential protection from iatrogenic muscle damage. *Annona muricata* leaves can also be explored as a complementary or synergistic strategy for managing medication mediated weight gain. However, further research with larger sample sizes and mechanism of action investigations are necessary to advance these findings.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflict of interests

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(Print) ISSN 3027-284X

Online: E-ISSN 3026-9245

Phytochemistry and Pharmacological Aspects,
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